

D6.5 – Roadmap towards replication (First version)

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ACL	Access Control List
ARM	Advanced RISC Machine
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CDC	Centralised Data Centre
COMTRADE	Common Format for Transient Data Exchange
DSoF	Digital Substation of the Future
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EU	European Union
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
FWA	Fixed Wireless Access
GA	Grant Agreement
GOOSE	Generic Object Oriented Substation Event
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HMAC	Hash-based Message Authentication Code
HSR	High-availability Seamless Redundancy
ICS	Industrial Control Systems
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IT	Information Technology
JOA	Joint Ownership Agreement
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KVM	Kernel-based Virtual Machine
LTE	Long-Term Evolution
MAC	Medium Access Control
MITM	Man-in-the-Middle
MMS	Manufacturing Message Specification
MPLS	Multiprotocol Label Switching
NIS	Network and Information Security Directive
NIS2	Revised Network and Information Security Directive
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OS	Operating System
OT	Operational Technology
PAC	Protection Automation Controller
PQ	Power Quality

PRP	Parallel Redundancy Protocol
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
R-GOOSE	Routed GOOSE
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RTDS	Real-Time Digital Simulator
RSTP	Rapid Spanning Tree Protocol
SAS	Substation Automation System
SV	Sampled Values
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TSO	Transmission System Operator
VTL	Virtualisation Testing Laboratory
vPAC	virtual Protection Automation Controller
VxLAN	Virtual Extensible LAN
WAN	Wide Area Network

Executive Summary

This deliverable, “Roadmap towards Replication (First Version)”, presents the initial strategic framework for the replication and large-scale deployment of the technological solutions developed within ESTELAR (Effective Substation Technologies for Advanced Virtualization) project. It provides a structured foundation for identifying the technical, regulatory and organisational conditions that enable the transition from demonstration results to broader implementation across Europe’s power systems. In this way, this document serves as a preliminary guide to identify pathways, enablers, and conditions necessary for scaling up and replicating the validated concepts of the Digital Substation of the Future (DSoF) across different energy systems and geographical contexts.

ESTELAR aims to contribute to the European Union’s energy transition goals by enhancing the resilience, flexibility, and cyber security of electrical substations through digitalization and virtualization. The project introduces an innovative DSoF concept, built upon three technological pillars: advanced communication strategies, distributed computing performance, and a modular virtualization architecture. These developments seek to transform the operation, maintenance, and interoperability of substations within the evolving smart grid ecosystem.

This first version establishes the methodological framework for future iterations of the roadmap, which will refine replication pathways, business models, and impact indicators. This roadmap builds on the experiences and lessons learned from the two Virtualization Testing Laboratories (VTLs) in Spain and the Netherlands, which act as foundational demonstrators for validating ESTELAR’s technologies in real-world-like environments. These facilities represent the first step toward demonstrating scalability, providing evidence for the technical feasibility and operational benefits of virtualized substations.

This document serves as a strategic tool for aligning technological outcomes with market and policy objectives, ensuring that ESTELAR contributes effectively to Europe’s digital and green transition by facilitating a secure, interoperable, and efficient modernization of the continent’s electrical infrastructure.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context and Objectives

ESTELAR (Effective Substation Technologies for Advanced Virtualization) is a Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action (RIA) with Grant Agreement No. 101192574 and coordinated by CIRCE. ESTELAR focuses on the development of virtualized, software-defined substation technologies designed to enhance interoperability, cybersecurity, flexibility, and cost efficiency across Europe's transmission and distribution grids. Moreover, ESTELAR brings together a multidisciplinary consortium of industrial, academic, and research partners to design, implement, and validate the *Digital Substation of the Future (DSoF)*. This concept decouples traditional, hardware-centric architectures from proprietary solutions, enabling a more interoperable, scalable, and secure energy system aligned with Europe's digital and green transition goals.

Within this framework, replication plays a crucial role in ensuring that ESTELAR's outcomes (ranging from software components, virtualization architectures, and communication frameworks to methodologies, operational procedures, and demonstration results) can be adopted and deployed across different contexts, grid typologies, and geographical areas. Replication is essential not only to achieve a wide market impact but also to accelerate the modernization and digital transformation of Europe's power infrastructure.

The deliverable D6.5 – Roadmap towards Replication (First Version) aims to establish the initial foundation for the systematic replication of ESTELAR's technological and methodological innovations beyond the project's pilot environments. It identifies the conditions, enablers, and barriers that influence large-scale adoption, considering technical, economic, organizational, and regulatory dimensions.

The specific objectives of this deliverable are:

- The definition of the replication concept and approach within ESTELAR, clarifying how the project's results can be scaled, transferred, or adapted to different operation and regulatory contexts.

- The identification and categorization of the main replication scenarios, considering the diversity of European energy systems, substation topologies, and stakeholder needs.
- The assessment of the technical enablers (e.g., interoperability, standardisation, modular design) and non-technical drivers (e.g., regulatory alignment, cost-benefit balance, business readiness) that determine replication potential.
- Establishing the methodological framework for measuring and validating replicability through future project iterations and stakeholder engagement.
- Providing an initial mapping between replicable components, demonstrator results, and target deployment environments to support future exploitation and policy alignment activities.

This first version establishes the baseline for a structured roadmap that will evolve throughout the project’s lifetime. It will be refined based on the results of the VTLs, stakeholder feedback, and ongoing assessment of regulatory and market conditions. Ultimately, this deliverable supports the long-term objective of translating ESTELAR’s innovations into replicable, interoperable, and market-ready solutions that reinforce Europe’s strategic autonomy and resilience in the energy sector.

1.2 Scope of the Deliverable

This deliverable D6.5 – Roadmap towards Replication (First Version) defines the initial framework and methodology for assessing, planning, and enabling the replication of ESTELAR’s technological, methodological, and operational outcomes beyond the scope of the project’s demonstration activities. It establishes the boundaries, objectives, and structure of the replication roadmap, providing a common reference for consortium partners, policymakers, and future adopters interested in ESTELAR’s results.

The scope of this first version is to provide a baseline understanding and procedure of how ESTELAR’s innovations focused on the DSoF can be transferred and adapted to real-world scenarios. This includes the virtualization, modularization, and software-defined control of substation functions, as well as their integration into existing and emerging grid architectures. The roadmap explores the replication potential of these solutions in different technical,

regulatory, and market contexts, while identifying the key challenges and enablers that influence their large-scale adoption.

This document is not intended to serve as a finalized replication plan; rather, it provides the first iteration of a structured, evidence-based methodology to guide future replication analysis within Work Package 6 (Exploitation, Replication and Business Models). It aligns with ongoing activities related to stakeholder engagement, business model definition, and exploitation planning, ensuring consistency across the project's strategic outputs. Future versions of the roadmap will be built upon this foundation in future deliverables D6.6 and D6.7, integrating findings from technical validation, demonstration results, and external feedback gathered throughout the project.

Specifically, this deliverable tackles the following aspects:

- Definition of the replication concept within ESTELAR and its relation to exploitation and scalability.
- Identification of replicable results, components, and processes in the VTLs.
- Preliminary analysis of the replication conditions and barriers, including technical readiness, interoperability, cost-benefit considerations, and regulatory alignment.
- First market analysis of ESTELAR's solutions to identify opportunities, potential risks and opportunities, understand competitors, and develop effective business plans for future exploitation.
- Proposal of a methodological framework for assessing replication potential in future project stages.
- Initial recommendations for stakeholder involvement and cooperation mechanisms to foster replication beyond the consortium.

Therefore, the scope of this document is both strategic and methodological. It sets the groundwork for an iterative process that will evolve as ESTELAR progresses, leading to a redefined *Roadmap towards Replication (Final Version)*. That future version will provide a more detailed, faithful and actionable pathway for the large-scale deployment of ESTELAR's outcomes.

1.3 Structure of the Document

This deliverable is organized into six main sections, each addressing a specific dimension of the roadmap development process and collectively providing a comprehensive overview of the current technological readiness, strategic advancement pathway, and replication potential of ESTELAR outcomes. The structure follows a logical progression – from assessing the present technological status to defining future actions for replication, commercialization, and risk management.

After this introduction section, in this deliverable we can find the following content:

- **Section 2: Current TRL Assessment (TRL Status).** This section provides a detailed analysis of the current TRL of the main ESTELAR components and technologies. It characterises the existing state of development, identifying maturity gaps, limitations, and opportunities for further enhancement. The subsections identified within this section address specific technological solutions studied in this project such as network architectures, communication technologies for critical infrastructures, unified hardware, DSoF and vPAC architectures, real time digital twins, and cyber-secure protection schemes.
- **Section 3: Strategic Roadmap for TRL Advancement.** Based on the assessment presented in Section 2, this section defines the strategic milestones and objectives necessary to advance the TRL of ESTELAR technologies. It outlines the concrete steps, interdependencies, and timeline required to achieve full validation and readiness for large-scale replication and deployment.
- **Section 4: Commercialization Pathways.** This section translates the technological developments into market-oriented actions. It includes a preliminary market analysis, identifies potential exploitations and business models, explores industry engagement strategies, and highlights regulatory and compliance considerations relevant to the adoption of ESTELAR's solutions in the European energy sector.
- **Section 5: Risk Assessment Mitigation.** This section analyses potential risks associated with the replication and commercialization of ESTELAR technologies. It evaluates technical, organisational, financial, and regulatory risks and proposes mitigations measures to ensure project robustness with both consortium objectives and EU policy frameworks.
- **Section 6: Conclusions and Next Steps.** This final section summarises the main findings of this first version of the roadmap and outlines the actions planned for the subsequent stages of the project.

Together, these sections provide a coherent framework for understanding ESTELAR's current technological maturity, defining the path towards its replication and large-scale deployment, and ensuring alignment with European priorities for digitalisation, resilience, and decarbonisation in the energy sector.

2 Current TRL Assessment (TRL Status)

This section presents a comprehensive assessment of the current Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the key technological processes and components developed within ESTELAR project, matching the most of them with the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) described in *Deliverable 6.4 Knowledge management and IPR protection plant (1st version)*. Its purpose is to establish a clear baseline of technological maturity, identifying the strengths, limitations, and advancement needs of the ESTELAR components prior to large-scale replication. This document does not redefine KERs but uses the KER structure and ownership defined in D6.4 to frame TRL evolution and replication readiness. Updates to KER definitions will be managed in D6.4 (coming updates) while the TRL mapping in D6.5 will follow those updates in later versions. The analysis covers the main functional domains of ESTELAR, including communication architectures, secure data exchange, computing performance, hardware unification, and cyber-secure protection schemes, as well as the overarching Digital Substation of the Future (DSoF) and virtual Process Automation Controller (vPAC) architectures. Each subsection, from 2.1 to 2.10, provides a detailed characterisation of the current development status, evaluating the sustainability of each technology for replication and deployment while highlighting the remaining steps required to reach higher TRLs in line with project objectives.

2.1 Current TRL Assessment – Advanced Communication Architecture

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).
The advanced communication architecture proposed in ESTELAR is currently at TRL 3, since the core design principles for integrating heterogeneous WAN technologies into a single framework suitable for critical infrastructure have been defined, but no full laboratory validation has yet taken place. Throughout the first year, the project has established the conceptual architecture, including multi-technology WAN integration, redundancy and failover strategies, secure tunnelling options, latency and jitter requirements, and the cybersecurity assumptions needed to support protection and control functions in a virtualised substation. These developments provide a coherent technical baseline, but the architecture

remains at an early maturity level. The target TRL for this component is TRL 5, which will be achieved once the communication architecture is implemented, integrated with the DSoF and vPAC components, and validated through controlled experiments in the CIRCE and TUD Virtual Testing Laboratories.

- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
So far, the project has defined the communication architecture in detail, identifying its functional requirements and aligning them with the needs of the Digital Substation of the Future and the virtual PAC framework. The performance criteria relevant for critical substation functions—such as latency, stability, jitter and packet loss—have been derived from the characterisation activities of T2.1, and a preliminary analysis has been carried out to determine the suitability of each WAN technology for protection, control, monitoring and digital twin applications. The high-level behaviour of redundancy mechanisms, routing strategies, and secure tunnelling solutions (notably VxLAN and Simplemux) has been established conceptually. Furthermore, the project has prepared the testing methodologies and use cases that will be applied in the next phases, ensuring that the future validation follows consistent procedures and reflects realistic operational needs.
- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
The next steps towards reaching TRL 5 involve implementing the routing strategies and secure tunnels defined in the architecture and validating their performance across different WAN technologies. Laboratory tests will be conducted to evaluate the behaviour of GOOSE and Sampled Values over fibre, LTE and satellite connections, assessing how the communication architecture handles impairments, failures and congestion. Inter-laboratory testing between CIRCE and CUERVA will enable validation of the architecture under real heterogeneous WAN conditions, providing end-to-end results that reflect the operational challenges of remote substations. Additional testing will be performed once the architecture is integrated with the digital twins and DSoF environments, enabling realistic scenarios that include grid disturbances, cyberattacks and complex routing conditions. These activities will allow the communication architecture to progress from conceptual design to prototype validation in relevant environments, meeting the requirements for TRL 5 and enabling future replication within WP6.

- Reference to tests or validations.

The validation of this architecture will be carried out primarily within Tasks 2.2 and 2.3, which will implement and test the communication channels, routing strategies and tunnelling mechanisms defined earlier in the project. The complete integration and evaluation will then take place within Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 through the Virtual Testing Laboratories of CIRCE and TUD, where the communication architecture will be tested together with the unified hardware, vPAC functionalities and digital twins. Further validation will also include inter-lab experiments between CIRCE and CUERVA using real WAN connections, ensuring that the architecture is assessed under representative operational conditions before progressing to replication activities.

2.2 Current TRL Assessment – Packet Communication Routing

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).

VxLAN and Simplemux are two tunnelling technologies that provide connection between different locations. They have been tested in a lab environment so far (see the research paper¹). Therefore, the corresponding TRL of the use of these technologies for creating secure tunnels is 3, “Applied research.”

VxLAN is already a standard, published by the IETF as an Independent Submission in 2014². Its implementation is a part of Linux, so it is mature and works in kernel space. However, its use as an alternative to R-GOOSE is still a research idea, explored in a research paper¹.

Simplemux is currently a research proposal which has been implemented in user space and tested in the lab³.

The objective of ESTELAR is to validate them as alternatives to R-GOOSE, in lab in a small-scale prototype (TRL 4).

¹ Saldana, J., Prada Hurtado, A. A., Martinez Carrasco, E., Galve, Y., & Torres, J. (2023). Fast and Reliable Sending of Generic Object Oriented Substation Event Frames between Remote Locations over Loss-Prone Networks. *Sensors*, 23(21), 8879.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/s23218879>

² RFC 7348: Virtual eXtensible Local Area Network (VXLAN): A framework for overlaying virtualized layer 2 networks over layer 3 networks. <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc7348>

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/17209552>

- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
The work with VxLAN and Simplemux is included in T2.3 *Routing and Network Strategies*, to be started in M13 (January 2026). This will be reported in Deliverable 2.2 *Communication channels and routing & network strategies*.

A research publication has been submitted regarding the Simplemux implementation, October 2025.

- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
T2.3 will implement these alternatives and will perform a battery of tests between different locations (Cuerva and CIRCE labs) connected via the technologies identified in T2.1.
- Reference to tests or validations (CIRCE/TUD VTLs, WP tasks, etc.).
The tests will be carried out as part of T2.3. Its objective is to *“implement and test different solutions for the secure and guaranteed sending of event-driven field commands (IEC 61850 GOOSE frames) between different locations.”* This will be reported in Deliverable 2.2 *Communication channels and routing & network strategies*.

2.3 Current TRL Assessment – Grid data Emulation

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).

This task will cover the generation of representative data sets to both (i) obtaining data repositories that may be shared publicly, dealing with the scarcity of this information and (ii) using the information on several tests of the project, mainly PQ applications or virtual IEDs. Therefore, the corresponding initial TRL of the use of these technologies is 4, “Laboratory testing of prototype component or process.”

- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
Tests were conducted to evaluate the operation of all the devices used to generate data. This allowed us to determine the operating range of the equipment as a whole in terms of current and voltage generation and amplification, as well as the configurations and wiring required between the different devices.

The results of the generation of dataset for PQ application will be reported in deliverable D2.3 Grid data repository and Common Data Spaces (December 2026)

- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
It is planned to maintain the current TRL (4 - “Laboratory testing of prototype component or process”) and, since the data set is public, the intention is to be able to replicate it.
- Reference to tests or validations.
In this case, the tests to be performed will be a sample of the IEC 61000-4-30 and IEC 62586-2 standards.

2.4 Current TRL Assessment – Computing Performance Baseline

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).
The task related to computing performance, focuses on the first specific analysis of computing needs and resources to be integrated in the ESTELAR resources, especially focused on the local level of VSs. One of the established guiding lines is the (ii) analysis of operating system performance, to be deployed on the local hardware itself or other suitable points of the end-to-end architecture.

This task is currently at TRL 4, corresponding to “Technology basic validation in a laboratory environment” stage. At this point, computing performance tests are being carried out on a developed local hardware in laboratory environment.

- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
Due to some deviations, the planned platform for the project is still under development. Therefore, a very similar hardware platform has been identified for testing the performance, both with same next-generation SoC FPGA with integrated ARM processors and high-speed interface. Same results expected for both platforms.

Computing performance for different OS solutions is still being under testing. The benchmark involves testing the hardware performance in different scenarios. The scenarios currently under testing are:

- Using Linux in bare metal
- Using a virtualized solution with Linux above KVM

CPU performance, memory usage, mutual exclusion, threading and disk performance has been tested. There are more benchmarking tools to be tested prior to defining the best benchmarking sheet.

In parallel, a Linux with PREEMT_RT is being set up and a FreeRTOS scenario is being defined.

- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
The planned actions are continuing with the testing of different scenarios for completing the whole intended benchmarking and obtaining relevant information for scenery comparison.

Once the Hardware performance under different scenarios is determined and which of the OS solutions is currently the best option for the purpose of the project is defined, it will be possible to start with the next stage. This stage will be TRL5, corresponding to “Prototype basic validation in a relevant environment” stage, which will be the development and validation of a prototype in environment that closely resembles real-world conditions. This is crucial to demonstrate the technology’s functionality, reliability and scalability. This stage will include testing in simulated operational settings or controlled industrial environments.

The results of the testing will be public and, since the required tools are open source, the replication of the test is granted.

- Reference to tests or validations.
The tests carried out through the benchmarking follow the usage and simplicity of the available options the Sysbench tool provides. The used version is sysbench 1.0.20.

The validation activities will be carried out within T5.4 (Testing and validation: CIRCE virtual laboratory), with final verification using the Virtual Testing Laboratories (VTLs) of CIRCE.

2.5 Current TRL Assessment – Reconfigurable Hardware Platform

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).
The task related to the development of a unified hardware, will focus on the first specific analysis of computing needs and resources to be integrated in the ESTELAR resources, especially focused on the local level of VSs. One of the established guiding lines is the (i) requirements identification and design of the hardware common platform for communication-based testing.

This task is currently at TRL 2, corresponding to “Technology concept or application formulated” stage. At this point, requirements for the hardware common platform have been defined and

- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
The needs and requirements for the hardware common platform, based on FPGA platform, including redundancy and synchronization technologies, HSR/PRP & TSN, and multi-core CPU with support to embedded OS, have been identified.

The hardware architecture has been also defined. This hardware is intended to implement HSR/PRP redundancy and SR-IOV capabilities for providing each virtual machine with direct, isolated hardware access to redundant network channels, merging real-time reliability with virtualized performance.

Due to some deviations in the hardware development, another, yet very similar, hardware in final phases of validation and prototyping have been selected for the testing phase, both with same next-generation SoC FPGA with integrated ARM processors and high-speed interface. Due to similarities in hardware, this will decrease significantly the expected validation and prototyping times for the final hardware.

Regarding the actual hardware, principal functionalities have been tested, while the computing performance benchmarking of the platform is being carried out.

- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
The planned actions are continuing with the benchmark, which will help determine the robustness of the developed hardware, while the final steps towards the final hardware validation and prototyping are being made. This will help step into TRL 3 and even TRL 4 sooner, shortening each stage periods.
- Reference to tests or validations.
The validation activities of the final hardware will be part of TRL5, corresponding to “Prototype basic validation in a relevant environment” stage, and will be carried out within T5.4 (Testing and validation: CIRCE virtual laboratory), with final verification using the Virtual Testing Laboratories (VTLs) of CIRCE.

2.6 Current TRL Assessment – DSoF Architecture

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).
This task will define DSoF architecture requirements, qualitatively compare different PAC architectures, and quantitatively evaluate the proposed architecture.
Currently, simple star and ring topologies have been tested in a limited experimental testbed with only a few IEC 61850-compliant IEDs connected to RTDS. This places the maturity of the current testing environment at TRL 3. By the end of the project, the identified optimal DSoF architecture will be deployed, implemented, and evaluated with a realistic digital substation deployment in the TUD lab. This will place the maturity of the final testing environment at TRL 4.
- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
DSoF architecture and performance requirements have been identified. Traditional PAC devices have been installed in the cabinets in a double-ring communication network configuration. The first ring enables station bus operations and relies on Rapid Spanning Tree Protocol (RSTP). The second ring enables process bus operations and relies on High-availability Seamless Redundancy Protocol (HSR).

- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
The planned actions include the complete installation and configuration of the DSoF. After the DSoF has been put into service, the provided performance in terms of redundancy, reliability, resiliency, and interoperability will be evaluated.
- Reference to tests or validations.
The testing of the identified DSoF architecture will be carried out in Task 5.3. The test will consist of verifying whether the identified architecture is capable of respecting the stringent timing and reliability requirements in both normal, fault, and cyber-attack conditions.

2.7 Current TRL Assessment – Digital Twinning

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).
This task will build a real-time digital twin, consisting of a combination of numerical models and powerful hardware, which behaves like the real power grid in every aspect.
Preliminary tests have been performed using a small power system simulated in RTDS and one IEC 61850-compliant IED. This places the maturity of the current digital twin technology at TRL 3.
With the deployment of DSoF, a wider power system model consisting of transmission and distribution systems will be simulated, with real-time interaction with the devices deployed in DSoF. This will place the maturity of the final digital twins environment at TRL 4.
- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
150 kV/10 kV transformers, power lines, busbar, and switchgear are currently successfully simulated in RTDS.
- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
The planned actions include: the testing of the 150 kV/10 kV transformers, power lines, busbars, and switchgears in RTDS; the deployment and testing of IED digital twins in Siemens Xcelerator cloud platform; and the deployment and testing of the power grid digital twin in RTDS.
- Reference to tests or validations.

The testing of the digital twins will be carried out in Task 5.3.

2.8 Current TRL Assessment – Virtualized PAC (vPAC)

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).
Currently, various PAC architectures are being explored to identify future PAC requirements that will then be addressed by the proposed vPAC architecture for centralized protection, automation, and control. The proposed DSoF architecture using vPAC will ensure interoperability and standardization.
With the deployment and testing of vPAC in DSoF, TRL 4 will be achieved.
- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
vPAC requirements have been identified. vPAC has been prototyped in Siemens labs.
- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
vPAC will be deployed in the DSoF to comprehensively mirror traditional PAC functionalities. The testing and validation of vPAC in DSoF will allow to reach TRL 4.
- Reference to tests or validations.
The testing of the digital twins will be carried out in Task 5.3. It will be assessed how vPAC performance compares to traditional PAC, and whether the stringent timing and reliability requirements are still met.

2.9 Current TRL Assessment – Cybersecurity Framework

- Current and target TRL (including justification or key results).
Different defensive measures and mitigation are being investigated to protect DSoF from various types of cyber attacks. These mitigations include: communication network micro-segmentation, Medium Access Control (MAC) address filtering with Access Control Lists (ACLs), HSR and PRP frames payload verification, replay protection for GOOSE and SV as specified in IEC 62351-6, IEEE 802.1X, IEEE 802.1AE, message authentication codes, and Transport Layer Security (TLS).

Moreover, a proof-of-concept implementation of HMAC to protect GOOSE messages has been tested in a basic testbed comprising one IEC 61850-compliant IED and RTDS. This places the maturity of the current DSoF cybersecurity assessment and cryptographic protocols implementation at TRL 3.

To reach TRL4, the cybersecurity of the DSoF assessment will be completed, and the most adequate security measures will be implemented and tested in DSoF.

- Main technical progress and validation activities achieved.
Different defensive measures have been qualitatively evaluated in terms of attack surface reduction, PAC availability, cost, and increased communication network complexity.
- Planned actions for TRL increase and replication.
Planned actions include the implementation of the most adequate defensive measures in DSoF and the further engineering and testing of our HMAC implementation in DSoF.
- Reference to tests or validations.
The testing and validation of the identified and deployed cybersecurity defensive measure will be carried out in Task 5.3. The proposed cybersecurity measures will be tested and demonstrated in DSoF with state-of-the-art PAC and vPAC systems.

3 Strategic Roadmap for TRL Advancement

This section intends to outline the strategic roadmap for the TRL advancement of the solutions proposed in ESTELAR. In that sense, this section includes the steps required to elevate the maturity of ESTELAR’s core technologies from their current development stage towards levels that enable their large-scale replication, commercial exploitation, and therefore, their integrations into operational environments. Building on the TRL assessment presented in Section 2, this section defines the milestones, dependencies, and activities that must be undertaken to progress toward higher TRLs in alignment with the project’s objectives, regulatory requirements, and future market adoption pathways.

The roadmap serves as a guiding framework that consolidates the technological evolution of the DSoF, the virtual Process Automation Controller (vPAC), unified hardware, secure communications, real-time digital twins, and advanced protection schemes. It also ensures coherence and link between research, demonstration, standardisation, and replication activities within ESTELAR and beyond.

The TRL advancement in ESTELAR requires a coordinated effort across technical work packages, pilot sites, industrial partners and external stakeholders such as DSOs, TSOs, regulatory agencies, standard bodies, and technology manufacturers. This section provides the overarching methodology for TRL progression and defines the specific milestones and actions necessary to ensure the ESTELAR’s technologies achieve the robustness, interoperability, cyber-resilience, and performance required for deployment in real-world substation environments. The TRL roadmap in D6.5 operationalises the exploitation intentions and KER portfolio of D6.4 (in §3.3), by specifying when KERs are expected to reach TRL levels that enable certain exploitation routes.

3.1 Milestones and objectives

Table 1. ESTELAR’s milestones and status.

Milestone description according to proposal	Status	Steps
1. Communications architecture ready and start of routing strategies (M12)	D2.1 delivered and approved by WP leader.	Start of T2.3: routing and network strategies

2. Computational operation benchmark finalised and DSoF and power grid digital twin ready (M18)	On going	D3.1 delivered and approved by WP leader. Architecture of DSoF and PAC architecture ready to be tested
3. ESTELAR monitoring and evaluation plan ready, start of validation tests (M21)	On going	ESTELAR technologies ready to be validated and tested in TUD and CIRCE VTLs. D5.1 checked and approved by WP leader and start of testing and validation campaign
4. All ESTELAR technologies developed and refined (M24)	On going	All technical deliverables checked and approved by WP leaders and coordinator
5. Main outcomes from VTLs testing and validation ready for upscaling (M28)	Not started	Representative results from the VTLs validation campaign available and fed into T6.6 to start with upscaling roadmap

The TRL advancement pathways in ESTELAR are structured around a set of project-defined milestones whose primary objective is to advance the targeted technologies up to TRL4. In addition, this deliverable defines forward-looking TRL progression pathways beyond TRL4, intended to guide future replication over a long-term horizon up to 8 years beyond the project lifetime.

Accordingly, the TRL advancement framework is organized into five sequential phases. Only Phases 1 and 2 fall within the direct implementation scope of ESTELAR, while Phases 3 to 5 describe the anticipated post-project evolution steps.

Phase 1 – Technical foundations (TRL2–3, in project): It focuses on establishing the technical foundations necessary for TRL2–3 progression. This includes completing the communications architecture and routing strategies (Stage 1) and finalising the technical requirements and DSoF/vPAC architecture (Stage 2). These activities ensure a stable design baseline aligned with IEC standards, cybersecurity guidelines, and project-wide interoperability needs.

Phase 2 – Laboratory validation in relevant environment (TRL3-4, in-project): it covers the transition from TRL3 to TRL4, through the preparation and execution of representative pilot demonstrations in the VTLs. This phase comprises the readiness of the computational benchmarking framework and digital twins (Stage 3), the establishment of the monitoring and evaluation framework and initiation of validation activities (Stage 4), integrated laboratory validation in the Virtual Test Labs (Stage 5), and the completion and refinement of the full ESTELAR technology stack (Stage 6). Together, these stages enable validation in controlled yet representative laboratory environments, consistent with TRL4 requirements.

Phase 3 – Pre-commercial validation (TRL5-7, post-project): This phase outlines a post-project evolution pathway toward TRL5 to 7, through pre-commercial demonstrations, including large-scale integrated system-level evaluations in the VTLs (Stage 7) and the consolidation of performance outcomes and validation evidence supporting scalability (Stage 8).

Phase 4 – Industrial adoption and deployment readiness (TRL7-8, post-project): Building on Phase 3, Phase 4 prepares the solutions for industrial adoption through the development of replication templates, compliance assessments, and deployment guidelines (Stage 9). This phase represents a medium to long-term step toward operational roll-out and standardised deployment.

Phase 5 – Industrialisation and market scale-up (TRL8-9, post-project): Finally, Phase 5 supports TRL8-9 maturity and post-project scale-up by consolidating the long-term roadmap for industrialisation, large-scale replication, lifecycle management, and market readiness (Stage 10). This phase represents a strategic outlook extending over an 8-year time horizon beyond the project completion.

Deepening into the stages conforming each of the phases of the roadmap for TRL advancement we can find:

Stage 1: Communications architecture ready and start of routing strategies (M1 - M12). The objective of this stage is to achieve a validated communication architecture serving as the baseline for the virtualised substation operation, in line with the first project milestone (see Table 1).

The completion of this stage marks the completion of the core communication design and the initial implementation of routing strategies essential for interoperability and real-time performance. This stage contributes to TRL3 consolidation, enabling early laboratory testing of network suitability, critical infrastructure communication technologies, secure tunnelling concepts, and

message flow optimisation. It also supports the interoperability foundations required for subsequent activities related to DSoF and vPAC integration.

Stage 2: Consolidation of technical requirements and DSoF/vPAC architecture (M1 – M24). The objective of this stage is to finalise the technical specifications for all ESTELAR components, ensuring alignment with IEC standards and cyber-security guidelines. Building on the communication architecture readiness defined in Stage 1, it focuses on completing the DSoF and vPAC requirements, validating technical assumptions, and ensuring system-level coherence across communications, computing, digital twins, protection schemes and unified hardware.

Stage 3: Computational operation benchmark finalised and DSoF and power grid digital twin ready (M1 – M18). This stage aims to provide a validated computational framework and digital twin environment to support system-level laboratory testing. It marks the readiness of the digital twin infrastructure and the definition of computational performance benchmarks for virtualised substation functions. The outputs of this stage provide the tools required for TRL4 validation, enabling analysis of latency, computing distribution, and power-quality data flows in controlled environments.

Stage 4: ESTELAR monitoring and evaluation plan ready, start of validation activities (M16 – M21). This stage aims to begin a structured validation in controlled environments. Together with the previous stage in which digital twins get ready, this establishes the monitoring framework, KPIs, testing plans and evaluation methodologies required to measure technology performance and TRL progression. This stage concurs with the third milestone (see Table 1), that officially launches the validation phase of ESTELAR technologies, enabling systematic assessment of communications, computing, cyber-security, interoperability, and DSoF functionalities in the VTLs.

Stage 5: Integration and validation in VTLs (M21 – M36). The objective of this stage is to validate interoperability and performance in controlled yet representative laboratory settings. It corresponds to the early implementation of the validation plan defined in stage 4 . It includes the integration of unified hardware, virtualised protection functions, digital twins, secure communication tunnels, PQ monitoring and distributed computing. TRL 4 is achieved and consolidated at the end of this stage.

Stage 6: All ESTELAR technologies developed and refined (M1 – M36). This stage focuses on completing the development and internal refinement of all core ESTELAR technologies. By The end of the project (M36), the full technology stack is established and validated in the laboratory environments, fully aligned with TRL4 objectives and the final project milestone.

Stage 7: Pre-deployment testing and system-level demonstration (M37 – M60). The objective in this stage is to demonstrate near-operational performance of ESTELAR solutions, advancing the solution from TRL5 to TRL6. After the full development reached in the previous stage, this stage focuses on running large-scale integrated tests in the VTLs that replicate realistic grid scenarios. This includes the execution of protection functions, control schemes, computing orchestration, cyber-resilience exercises and end-to-end communication flows.

Stage 8: Consolidation of validation evidence for upscaling (M60 – M84). This stage aims to validate evidence that supports widespread adoption. By M84, a consolidated set of demonstration outcomes could be delivered, performance benchmarks, and validated technical results. This stage is key for replication as it documents the maturity and readiness of the technologies to progress towards TRL 7 and future real-world deployment.

Stage 9: Preparation for replication and industrial adoption (M84 – M108). Once the validation is ready for upscaling, the objective in this stage is to develop replication templates, compliance assessments and deployment guidance. It includes replication scenarios, cost-benefit analysis, stakeholder engagement, and preparation for future standardisation contributions if applies.

Stage 10: Roadmap consolidation for large-scale deployment (M108 – M120). This stage aims to provide long-term strategic guidance for large-scale replication. In this stage it is necessary to identify industrialisation pathways, and establish long-term strategies for deployment, lifecycle management and maintenance.

Figure 1. Roadmap to commercialization.

3.2 Steps supporting roadmap implementation

The achievement of the aforementioned stages and milestones defined in the ESTELAR roadmap requires a structured sequence of technical, organizational, and validation actions. These actions can be grouped into a set of steps that ensure each technological component advances coherently across TRL levels, while maintaining interoperability, regulatory alignment, cybersecurity measures, and readiness for future replication. Decisions on when/how to move from one TRL phase to commercial exploitation (e.g., moving from VTL validation to licensing or productisation) will follow the governance, JOAs, and access-rights processes defined in D6.4 §2.3–4.1. These steps are described as follows:

Step 1: Reinforcing technical foundations and standard alignment (supports M12)
 The first step focuses on establishing a robust foundation for the project's technological development. This involves:

- Finalising technical specifications for communications, DSoF architecture, vPAC design, unified hardware platforms, computing layers and cybersecurity modules.
- Ensuring alignment with international standards (e.g., IEC 61850, IEC 62351, IEEE standards for time synchronization and communication performance), which is essential to guarantee interoperability of virtualized substation functions.
- Developing the communication architecture, including time-sensitive networks, routing strategies, and secure tunnelling capabilities, to reach the first milestone by M12.

This step marks the consolidation from conceptual development (TRL 3) to readiness for laboratory validation (TRL 4).

Step 2: Component prototyping, harmonisation and integration preparation (supports M6 to M21). This step ensures that components are aligned and ready for integrated laboratory validation in support of TRL 4.

Once the main requirements are in place, the next step is to develop functional prototypes and prepare them for integrated evaluation. This includes:

- Developing individual software and hardware modules, such as edge computing nodes, vPAC functions, PQ monitoring tools, digital twin models, and cyber-secure communications modules.
- Running initial functional tests within each partner's laboratory environment to verify conformity with specifications.
- Harmonising data exchange interfaces, including semantic interoperability, latency requirements, and security mechanisms.
- Preparing the computational benchmarking framework, which assess performance under realistic load conditions and contributes directly to the second milestone (see Table 1).
- Building the DSoF and grid digital twins, including real-time simulation capabilities for the VTLs.

Step 3: Deployment of the monitoring and evaluation framework (supports M16 – M21).

A robust validation is of utmost importance in order to assess TRL progression.

Actions in this step includes:

- Finalising the ESTELAR monitoring and evaluation plan, defining KPIs, test scenarios, boundary conditions, cyber-security metrics, and interoperability criteria.
- Setting up testing workflows for both VTLs, including test automation, fail-safe conditions, and safety procedures.
- Coordinating test responsibilities among partners to ensure consistency across validation cycles.
- Launching the first structured validation tests in the VTLs, as required to reach the third milestone "Start of validation tests" (see Table 1).

Step 4: Integration and validation across the VTLs (supporting M21 to M36).

This step covers the detailed integration and testing of all ESTELAR components in controlled environments. This step ensures consolidation and validation of the

integrated ESTELAR technology stack at TRL 4 in controlled laboratory environments.

The actions to reach that TRL level are as follows:

- Integrating all developed technologies into each VTL following a phased integration approach.
- Conducting iterative validation cycles, allowing identification of performance deviations, vulnerabilities, and interoperability issues.
- Optimising algorithms, refining interfaces, and implementing corrective actions based on validation feedback.
- Completing technology development and refinement for all components by M24, reaching the fourth milestone “All ESTELAR technologies developed and refined”.

Step 5: Extended laboratory testing and consolidation of validation outcomes.

Beyond the project lifetime, further validation activities may be carried out to consolidate laboratory results and prepare for future replication. These activities may include:

- Executing complex test scenarios that simulate realistic grid conditions, including protection schemes, communication failures, cyber-attacks, overload situations, or PQ disturbances.
- Assessing integrated behaviour under controlled but increasingly complex conditions.

Step 6: Replication preparation and industrial readiness.

Once there are validated results available, technologies can be prepared for future replication and industrial deployment. These activities define a long-term pathway beyond TRL 4:

- Developing replication blueprints, including network configurations, hardware requirements and setup, deployment procedures and cyber-security guidelines.
- Performing a regulatory analysis to identify compliance needs regarding EU network codes, cybersecurity directives and digitalisation policies.
- Mapping scalability options for different grid configurations, voltage levels, and operational environments.
- Engaging DSOs, TSOs, manufacturers and standardisation bodies for collecting feedback for industrial adoption.

Step 7: Consolidation of long-term roadmap and post-project exploitation.

The final step toward replication ensures the long-term sustainability of ESTELAR outcomes:

- Integrating lessons learned from testing, validation, and stakeholder engagement into a consolidated roadmap.
- Identifying innovation gaps, future research opportunities, and potential contributions to EU standardisation activities.
- Defining a high-level exploitation strategy, linking TRL growth to business models, market opportunities, and industrial partnerships.
- Providing guidance for large-scale replication beyond the project timeline.

It is worth highlighting that steps 1 to 4 describe the actions required to achieve the project milestones and reach TRL4 by M36, and steps 5 to 7 describe a forward-looking post-project pathway.

4 Commercialization Pathways

The commercialisation of ESTELAR's outcomes requires a clear understanding of the market context, the potential exploitation routes for the project's results, the level of engagement with industrial stakeholders and the regulatory factors that may influence adoption. This chapter provides an integrated view of these elements, linking the technical achievements of ESTELAR with the conditions necessary for their effective uptake beyond the project.

Section [4.1](#) analyses the market landscape and identifies the drivers, barriers and readiness factors relevant to digital substation technologies.

Section [4.2](#) outlines the main exploitable results generated by the project and describes the potential business models and value propositions they enable.

Section [4.3](#) summarises how ESTELAR interacts with industry partners and external stakeholders to ensure the relevance and applicability of its developments.

Finally, Section [4.4](#) examines the regulatory and compliance context at European and national levels, highlighting the conditions that will shape future replication to real-world environments.

Together, these elements form the basis for defining the commercial and operational pathways through which ESTELAR can generate long-term impact.

4.1 Market Analysis

The core market characterisation and segmentation follow D6.4 §3.1.

This section does not introduce new figures or divergent segment definitions, but interprets them from a replication-roadmap perspective (e.g., which segments are most suitable for early replication).

4.1.1 Scope of the ESTELAR Market

ESTELAR addresses a set of technologies positioned at the core of substation digitalisation. The project does not produce a single commercial product, but rather an integrated suite of:

- Virtualised protection and control architectures (vPAC).
- Advanced communication mechanisms and benchmarking of WAN technologies for remote substation operation.

- Tools and methodologies for digital data generation and processing (Sampled Values, COMTRADE-based datasets, data repositories).
- Digital twins for substation components and protection systems.
- Cybersecurity-by-design mechanisms applied to critical infrastructures.

Therefore, the relevant “market” for ESTELAR is not a standalone product category but an ecosystem of solutions, methods and capabilities that can be adopted by network operators, vendors, integrators and research bodies supporting the modernisation of substation automation systems.

4.1.2 Target Market Segments and Stakeholders

Based on the stakeholders represented in the consortium and the needs identified in the project proposal, the target market for ESTELAR can be segmented as follows:

Primary segments

- Distribution System Operators (DSOs): responsible for deploying and operating substations, and the main adopters of virtualised, interoperable and remotely managed architectures.
- Transmission System Operators (TSOs): benefitting from advanced protection schemes, digital twins and wide-area coordination mechanisms.

Secondary segments

- Substation automation and protection vendors (Intelligent Electronic Devices (IEDs), Merging Units, vPAC platforms).
- Communication technology and network equipment providers (routers, 4G/5G, fibre, FWA, satellite).
- OT/ICS cybersecurity companies looking to validate architectures under realistic scenarios.
- Research laboratories, technical centres and universities involved in certification, testing and demonstration activities.

These actors form the broader market environment in which ESTELAR’s results can create value, supporting the transition towards digital, interoperable and virtualised substations.

4.1.3 Market Needs and Drivers

The proposal highlights several structural pressures affecting modern substations, including the integration of renewable generation, decentralisation, electrification, and increased operational complexity. D6.4 (Knowledge management and IPR protection plan) contains a detailed and quantitative market/business model analysis, while this document summarises and reuses that work, focusing on how it supports replication and TRL advancement. In this context, several drivers strengthen the relevance of ESTELAR:

a) Digitalisation of the electricity system

Enhanced visibility, automation and responsiveness are required to manage increasingly complex grids, reinforcing the role of DSoF, vPAC and virtualised architectures.

b) Limitations of traditional communication infrastructures

Dedicated lines are increasingly impractical. ESTELAR addresses scenarios involving fibre, 4G/5G, radio and satellite, fully aligned with industry trends towards heterogeneous WAN technologies.

c) Growing cybersecurity requirements

The proposal describes potential cyberattacks (MITM, spoofing, replay) and the need for robust protection mechanisms. Evolving EU cybersecurity frameworks further increase the demand for validated, secure architectures.

d) Need for interoperability and reduced vendor lock-in

The use of IEC 61850 (GOOSE, SV, MMS, 90-5), multivendor validation and data-centric operation reflects a strong market push towards interoperability.

e) Virtualisation as an emerging trend

The move from hardware-based PAC to virtualised PAC, supported by cloud/edge computing, aligns closely with the architectural concepts validated in DSoF.

Together, these drivers indicate that ESTELAR is positioned in a market undergoing structural transformation.

4.1.4 Barriers and Constraints to Adoption

Despite favourable conditions, several barriers may slow down the uptake of ESTELAR outcomes:

a) Technical barriers

- Strict real-time requirements for virtualised protection (latencies in the 3–5 ms range).
- Dependency on WAN quality in heterogeneous network environments.
- Architectural differences between advanced laboratory setups and existing substations.
- Interoperability challenges across vendors.

b) Organisational barriers

- Limited availability of personnel with expertise in IEC 61850, advanced cybersecurity or digital twins.
- Traditional separation between OT and IT domains.
- Different levels of digital maturity across DSOs and TSOs.

c) Economic barriers

- Initial investment required for transitioning to virtualised or edge/cloud-enabled solutions.
- Replacement of legacy protection and automation systems.

d) Regulatory barriers

- Compliance with standards such as IEC 61850-3, IEC 62351 or equivalent certification schemes.
- Alignment with evolving EU frameworks on digitalisation and cybersecurity.
- Requirements for certification of protection functions.
- These barriers define the conditions under which ESTELAR results can be scaled beyond laboratory environments.

4.1.5 Competitive and Solution Landscape

Current substation automation environments rely on:

- Traditional SAS architectures built around dedicated IED hardware.
- Limited virtualisation.
- Vendor-specific solutions with varying degrees of interoperability.
- Communication systems based on dedicated or MPLS lines.
- Tightly coupled protection functions.

ESTELAR introduces several differentiating elements:

- Validated virtualisation (vPAC) under real-time constraints.

- Benchmarking of multiple WAN technologies.
- Reusable digital twins and data-driven workflows.
- Secure and scalable substation architectures.
- Data-centric approaches such as virtual CDC.
- Multivendor interoperability validation.
- Demonstration across two complementary VTLs (CIRCE and TUD).

These capabilities position ESTELAR not as a competing product but as an enabler of next-generation substation technologies.

4.1.6 Market Readiness and Alignment with TRL

According to the proposal, the technologies addressed in ESTELAR start at TRL 3–4. Validation within both VTLs enables:

- The demonstration of technical feasibility
- The generation of empirical evidence.
- The identification of deployment prerequisites.
- The progression towards pre-pilot environments (TRL 5).

Industry readiness follows a similar pattern:

- Strong interest in virtualisation and cybersecurity.
- Growing adoption of IEC 61850-based systems.
- Limited deployment of fully virtualised or cloud-supported protection functions.

This defines a window of opportunity in which:

- Innovation-driven DSOs (such as those in the consortium) act as early adopters,
- Vendors can incorporate findings into new product generations,
- The sector can progressively transition towards the digital and virtualised substation concepts validated by ESTELAR.

4.2 Exploitation and Business Models

The definition of KERs, protection strategies and business models is given in D6.4 (§3.2–3.3). D6.5 simply maps those existing exploitation approaches onto TRL/replication steps (e.g., how increasing TRL enables specific models). For further information see D6.4 as the reference document for detailed KER and business model descriptions.

4.2.1 Main exploitable results of ESTELAR

ESTELAR generates a set of outcomes with clear exploitation potential across the substation automation and energy digitalisation domains. These results emerge from the work conducted in WP2–WP5 and cover communication, virtualisation, data-centric operation and cybersecurity aspects. These exploitable results are consistent with and derived from the KERs identified in D6.4, consequently, any formal change to the list of core exploitable results/KERs will be reflected first in updates of D6.4 (coming updates), and D6.5 will be aligned accordingly in its future versions. The main exploitable results include:

- Communication benchmarking and WAN characterisation, encompassing comparative assessments of fibre, 4G/5G, radio and satellite links, as well as controlled WAN degradation profiles relevant for remote substation operation.
- Virtualised protection and control concepts (vPAC), including architectural frameworks, real-time performance analyses and validation workflows.
- Digital twins for power grids, IEDs and PAC systems, which enable reproducible validation scenarios and support configuration management, firmware testing and interoperability assessments.
- Virtual Centralised Data Centre (virtual CDC) workflows, supporting data-centric substation operation and the integration of digital measurement, storage and processing chains.
- Cybersecurity validation methodologies, including the testing of attack scenarios (MITM, spoofing, replay) and corresponding mitigation techniques aligned with IEC 62351-6.
- Datasets, testing methods and validation procedures, enabling reproducible experiments, training, benchmarking and future research activities.

These outcomes form the basis for exploitation activities extending beyond the project's timeframe.

4.2.2 Exploitation pathways by stakeholder group

The exploitable results of ESTELAR are relevant to several categories of stakeholders in the energy and industrial automation sectors. Each group can derive value from adopting, adapting or further developing the outcomes validated within the project.

Distribution System Operators (DSOs)

DSOs can use ESTELAR's communication benchmarking to support technology selection and planning for WAN-based substation connectivity. Virtualised protection and control concepts enable long-term migration paths away from hardware-based architectures, while datasets and validation procedures support internal testing, auditing and training.

Transmission System Operators (TSOs)

TSOs may benefit from digital twins, advanced protection schemes and data-centric operation concepts, enabling improved coordination across wide-area protection systems and more accurate assessment of contingency scenarios.

Substation automation and protection vendors

Vendors can leverage virtualised PAC concepts and interoperability results to design next-generation products compliant with IEC 61850 and aligned with virtualised or hybrid architectures. Digital twins and associated validation methods provide tools for prototyping, regression testing and performance benchmarking.

Communication technology providers

Providers of fibre, wireless or satellite communication services can use WAN characterisation outputs to validate the suitability of their solutions for mission-critical energy applications, and to define service profiles and quality-of-service offerings.

OT/ICS cybersecurity companies

Cybersecurity firms may exploit the attack scenarios, testing workflows and mitigation strategies to develop new tools, services or certification frameworks tailored to digital substations.

Research laboratories and technical centres

These actors can reuse datasets, testing procedures and digital twins for further research, certification activities, interoperability testing or educational purposes.

4.2.3 Business model options

The exploitable results of ESTELAR can support several business model configurations, depending on the stakeholder type and the maturity of the underlying technologies.

Software and licensing models

Some outcomes, such as IEC 61850 analysis tools, digital twins or virtual CDC components, could be further developed into software packages or licensed modules.

Services and consultancy models

ESTELAR outcomes enable consultancy services in areas such as communication performance assessment, migration to virtualised protection systems, cyber-resilience validation and interoperability testing.

Platform-based models (PaaS)

Virtual CDC workflows and cloud/edge-enabled architectures could evolve into platform-based services offering secure processing environments for digital substation applications.

Training and certification models

Datasets, testing methods and cybersecurity validation scenarios could support specialised training programmes, certification schemes or professional development courses.

Collaborative and open innovation models

Some results, such as datasets or high-level validation procedures, may be shared under open or collaborative frameworks to support broader adoption and community-driven improvement.

This is worth noting that the primary definition and allocation of business models to partners and KERs is in D6.4 §3.2. This document highlights those business model types that are most relevant for replication and TRL progression, not to redefine them.

4.2.4 Value proposition

The collective value proposition of ESTELAR's exploitable results can be summarised as follows:

- Reduced CAPEX and OPEX through virtualisation, enabling more efficient lifecycle management of protection and control systems.
- Improved resilience and cybersecurity, supported by validated attack scenarios and mitigation workflows.

- Enhanced interoperability across vendors through IEC 61850-based validation and testing procedures.
- Greater flexibility in WAN integration, enabling substation connectivity through fibre, 4G/5G, radio or satellite technologies.
- Full digitalisation of testing and operational workflows based on reproducible datasets and digital twins.
- Replicable validation evidence, thanks to coordinated testing activities in the project's Virtualisation Testing Laboratories.

These benefits align with ongoing trends in the energy sector and address key operational challenges faced by network operators and industrial stakeholders.

4.2.5 Alignment with TRL and commercial maturity

The technologies addressed in ESTELAR are positioned at TRL 3 at the start of the project. Validation performed within the VTLs supports progression towards TRL 4, enabling a clearer understanding of deployment requirements and performance boundaries.

From a commercial maturity perspective:

- Virtualisation, data-centric operation and WAN-enabled protection are emerging but not yet mainstream in substation automation.
- DSOs with strong innovation agendas, such as those within the consortium, represent natural early adopters.
- Vendors can incorporate ESTELAR results into future product lines or service offerings.
- Medium-term opportunities exist for platform-based services, interoperability testing and cybersecurity validation.

In summary, ESTELAR provides a foundation for subsequent phases of commercialisation and product development, enabling future large-scale adoption of digital and virtualised substation technologies.

4.3 Industry Engagement

Industry engagement is essential to ensure that ESTELAR's technical developments are aligned with the operational needs and priorities of the electricity sector. The project combines validation activities performed within the Virtualisation Testing Laboratories (VTLs) with the active involvement of industrial partners, whose

perspectives help steer the work towards practical and future-oriented adoption paths.

4.3.1 Contribution of industrial partners within the consortium

The industrial partners in ESTELAR bring direct operational and market-oriented insight that strengthens the relevance of the project outcomes:

- DSOs (CUERVA and STEDIN) contribute their practical experience in operating real distribution networks and managing heterogeneous communication infrastructures. Their role is not to act as test environments, but to provide requirements, operational constraints and perspectives on feasibility. In the case of CUERVA, their WAN infrastructure offers a practical reference that complements the laboratory capabilities without constituting a formal testing site.
- Technology providers (such as Siemens) contribute expertise in protection and control systems, substation digitalisation and product roadmaps, ensuring alignment between ESTELAR developments and industry trends.
- SOC-E, as a specialist in industrial communications and OT cybersecurity, contributes technologies and operational knowledge related to synchronisation, critical networking and cyber-protection mechanisms.
- R2M provides expertise in exploitation, business modelling and communication strategies, supporting the translation of technical results into pathways for adoption and impact.

The diversity of these roles ensures that technical activities are continuously informed by operational, commercial and regulatory perspectives. The formal governance of exploitation and IPR decisions (e.g., prioritisation of KERs for market uptake) is defined in D6.4 §4. The roles described in this document concern replication and TRL activities, which feed back into those governance structures.

4.3.2 Engagement through VTL-based activities

The CIRCE and TUD VTLs serve as the primary platforms where ESTELAR technologies are validated and demonstrated. Industrial engagement in this context could take the form of:

- Technical review sessions.
- Demonstrations and analysis of validation results.
- Discussions on applicability under real-world conditions.
- Iterative feedback loops between industrial partners and technical teams.

This interaction allows operators, vendors and specialists to evaluate the behaviour of the validated solutions and to assess their relevance for future deployment scenarios.

4.3.3 Dissemination activities and technical dialogue with the wider industry

Beyond the internal collaboration within the consortium, ESTELAR promotes interaction with the broader industry community through activities such as:

- Technical workshops, webinars and public demonstrations.
- Participation in conferences and sectoral forums on smart grids, digitalisation and cybersecurity.
- Contributions to standardisation groups related to IEC 61850 and digital substation architectures.
- Dissemination of datasets, validation methodologies and technical documentation.

These mechanisms support knowledge transfer and enable external stakeholders to gain early visibility of the project's results.

4.3.4 Future engagement and adoption pathways

As ESTELAR progresses towards higher levels of validation maturity, the project aims to strengthen its interaction with:

- Additional DSOs and TSOs interested in virtualisation, interoperability and advanced communication technologies,
- Vendors exploring the evolution towards vPAC and data-centric architectures,
- Communication providers seeking to support energy sector applications,
- Experts in cybersecurity and regulatory bodies,
- Research organisations and academic institutions.

These engagement pathways are essential to position ESTELAR outcomes within the wider industrial landscape and to establish the foundations for future replication and adoption.

4.4 Regulatory and Compliance Considerations

The replication of ESTELAR's results depends not only on their technical and economic feasibility but also on their alignment with the regulatory and compliance frameworks applicable to digital substations and critical infrastructures. This section provides an overview of the main technical standards,

cybersecurity requirements and regulatory contexts relevant to the project, with specific consideration of the European framework and the national contexts of Spain and the Netherlands, where the project's VTLs are located.

4.4.1 Technical standards and interoperability

ESTELAR builds upon established international standards for digital substations and industrial communication systems, which enables interoperability and facilitates future certification:

- IEC 61850, covering GOOSE, Sampled Values (SV), MMS and extensions such as 61850-90-5 for IP-based communications.
- PTP / IEEE 1588 for time synchronisation, essential for aligning digital measurements and events under real-time conditions.
- IEC 62351-6 and related cybersecurity mechanisms, supporting the protection of GOOSE/SV messages and ensuring the integrity and authenticity of communications.

The use of these standards:

- Reduces vendor lock-in risks.
- Supports integration across multivendor environments.
- Aligns with technical certification requirements applied by regulators and network operators.

From a replication perspective, the fact that ESTELAR's architectures follow the IEC 61850 + IEC 62351 + PTP paradigm facilitates their adoption across Member States, including Spain and the Netherlands, where these standards are already widely used in digitalisation initiatives.

4.4.2 Cybersecurity and critical infrastructure requirements

Electrical substations are classified as critical or essential entities in most EU Member States, and are therefore subject to specific cybersecurity obligations.

European level

At EU level, the regulatory framework is currently shaped by:

- The NIS2 Directive, which broadens the scope of essential entities and strengthens obligations on risk management, incident response, technical measures and reporting.

- The Directive on the resilience of critical entities, which reinforces physical, organisational and operational requirements for essential services, including the energy sector.
- The EU Digitalisation of Energy Action Plan, which highlights the need to combine digitalisation with cybersecurity, interoperability and secure data handling.

ESTELAR contributes indirectly to these compliance requirements by:

- Evaluating the behaviour of virtualised PAC architectures and WAN-based communication schemes under cyberattacks such as MITM, replay or spoofing.
- Validating protection mechanisms aligned with IEC 62351-6 and defence-in-depth practices.
- Providing testing methodologies and structured evidence that can support cybersecurity assessments.

Spain (CIRCE laboratory)

In Spain, the regulatory framework applicable to energy infrastructures includes:

- Law 8/2011 on the protection of critical infrastructures, defining obligations for operators of critical infrastructure in coordination with the national authorities.
- Royal Decree-Law 12/2018, implementing the original NIS Directive and establishing cybersecurity obligations for essential and digital service providers.
- Royal Decree 43/2021, which operationalises the national NIS framework, defining competent authorities, supervision mechanisms and incident reporting procedures.
- The ongoing transposition of NIS2, which will expand the number of affected entities and strengthen requirements for risk management, governance and reporting.

For future replication in Spain, it will be necessary to ensure that ESTELAR-derived solutions integrate with the cybersecurity management systems required under this framework. The project's use of open standards and documented validation methods eases this alignment.

Netherlands (TUD laboratory)

In the Netherlands, the applicable framework includes:

- The Wbni (Network and Information Systems Security Act), which implemented the first NIS Directive and set security and reporting obligations for essential services, including energy.
- The upcoming Cyberbeveiligingswet (Cybersecurity Act), which will transpose NIS2 and introduce reinforced requirements for risk management, governance and incident notification.
- The Dutch Cybersecurity Strategy 2022–2028, identifying energy networks as vital sectors and emphasising the need to strengthen digital resilience.

The validation results produced in the TUD VTL can support operators and vendors working in the Dutch market by providing technical evidence regarding the behaviour of digital substation architectures under fault and attack conditions.

4.4.3 Data governance and digitalisation frameworks

ESTELAR's work on virtual CDC concepts, data-centric operation and structured datasets aligns with broader European trends in data governance and sector digitalisation.

The EU Digitalisation of Energy Action Plan recognises the importance of data interoperability, cybersecurity and the secure handling of operational data, and promotes the development of energy data spaces and common frameworks for data exchange.

In this context, ESTELAR's outcomes:

- Support the treatment of substation data as a structured and reusable asset (digital measurements, events, protection records).
- Introduce workflows for digital measurement processing and storage compatible with secure data governance models.
- Provide examples of responsible use of operational data for validation, training and resilience analysis.

Both Spain and the Netherlands apply data protection and information security frameworks (including GDPR where applicable and sector-specific rules for sensitive infrastructure data). The data-centric approaches developed in ESTELAR must be integrated into the internal data policies of each operator and national requirements for secure data handling.

4.4.4 Regulatory constraints and implications for replication

Across the EU, and specifically in Spain and the Netherlands, the replication of ESTELAR's results will depend on:

- Compliance with the technical standards applicable to digital substations (IEC 61850, IEC 62351, PTP), which facilitates the certification and deployment of the validated architectures.
- Alignment with NIS/NIS2 requirements and their national transpositions (Spain's RDL 12/2018 and RD 43/2021; the Dutch Wbni and forthcoming Cyberbeveiligingswet), which mandate systematic risk management, appropriate technical and organisational measures, and formalised incident reporting.
- The classification of substations as critical or essential infrastructures, implying additional requirements for physical protection, operational resilience and continuity.

In practice, this means that:

Any deployment derived from ESTELAR must be embedded within the operator's existing security management systems.

- The testing methods and validation evidence generated in the VTLs can be reused to support regulatory risk assessments and compliance documentation.
- The adoption of ESTELAR-based solutions will be smoother for organisations already adapting their processes to NIS2 and related national frameworks.

Overall, ESTELAR's focus on standards-based design, cybersecurity and data governance is coherent with the direction set by European and national regulation and provides a solid foundation for future replication of its results in regulated operational environments.

5 Risk assessment and Mitigation Measures for Future Replication

The deployment and replication of ESTELAR technologies beyond the project's Virtualisation Testing Laboratories (VTLs) is exposed to a number of technical, organisational and contextual risks. These risks may affect the ability of system operators and industry stakeholders to adopt the proposed architectures, to reproduce the performance demonstrated in the laboratories, or to integrate the solutions into their existing operational environments.

This chapter provides a structured assessment of such risks and outlines the corresponding mitigation strategies. It builds on the overall project risk management approach defined in the Grant Agreement – where generic project, management and technical risks are identified and monitored – and refines it from the specific perspective of replication and scale-up of the ESTELAR results.

The analysis focuses on risks that are directly linked to the use and outcomes of the two ESTELAR VTLs:

- The CIRCE Virtualisation Testing Laboratory (Digital SAS and communications), used to validate communication channels, data acquisition and virtualisation workflows.
- The TU Delft Digital Substation of the Future (DSoF) laboratory, used to validate real-time operation, virtualised PAC (vPAC), digital twins and cyber-secure protection schemes.

For each VTL, the chapter identifies:

- The main risks that could limit the transferability and replicability of the validated solutions.
- Their potential impact on TRL advancement and on large-scale deployment.
- And the mitigation measures that can be applied within the project and in future roll-outs.

The chapter concludes with a consolidated risk table that summarises the most relevant risks, their likelihood and impact, and the proposed mitigation strategies, providing a clear input to the overall replication roadmap developed in D6.5. Finally, this is worth noting the D6.4 already covers IPR and exploitation-related risks in detail, while D6.5 focuses specifically on technical and contextual risks that

affect replication of VTL-validated solutions, and should be read in conjunction with the IPR risk framework of D6.4 (§5).

5.1 Risk assessment and mitigation measures related to CIRCE Virtualisation Testing Laboratory

The CIRCE Virtualisation Testing Laboratory (Digital SAS and communications) plays a central role in validating the communication technologies, virtualisation workflows and data acquisition strategies developed in ESTELAR. As this laboratory integrates both controlled WAN emulation environments and real connectivity conditions through CUERVA’s operational infrastructure, it provides a representative basis for assessing the applicability of the project’s solutions.

However, several risks may affect the transferability and replicability of the results generated in this VTL. These risks relate to the coverage of communication scenarios, the use of laboratory-specific equipment, interoperability constraints, dataset representativeness and the differences between controlled and real environments. The following tables identify these risks and outlines their corresponding mitigation measures, ensuring that the outcomes produced in the CIRCE–CUERVA VTL can be reliably interpreted and reused in future deployments.

Table 2. Risk assessment and mitigation measures for the CIRCE Virtualisation Testing Laboratory

Risk ID	Risk description	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation strategy
R1	Incomplete coverage of real-world communication scenarios across the CIRCE–CUERVA VTL.	Medium	High	Combine laboratory WAN emulation with real operator connectivity in CUERVA, prioritising representative use cases and documenting the scope and limitations of each validated scenario.
R2	Dependency on laboratory-specific hardware for the virtual CDC.	Low	Medium	Document minimum hardware requirements and provide hardware-agnostic performance indicators to facilitate

				deployment on alternative platforms.
R3	Interoperability constraints across multivendor IEC 61850 IED implementations.	Medium	Medium	Use the multivendor IEC 61850 environment to identify vendor-specific behaviours and produce clear replication guidelines on validated functions.
R4	Limited generalisability of datasets generated in the VTL.	Medium	Medium	Generate datasets from multiple sources (synthetic and analogue) and provide detailed metadata and validation context to clarify applicability.
R5	Variability of real-world WAN technologies limiting applicability of laboratory results.	Medium	High	Validate communication technologies through both emulated tests and CIRCE-CUERVA cross-site evaluations, producing performance ranges aligned with WP2's methodology.
R6	Differences between laboratory-grade and field-grade equipment.	Low	Medium	Document which functions depend on specialised laboratory equipment and validate key behaviours using CUERVA's operational infrastructure where possible.
R7	Limited transferability of performance results obtained under controlled WAN degradation.	Low	Medium	Complement degradation profiles with real communication traces and identify worst-case patterns relevant for replication.

R8	Dependency on CIRCE's in-house IEC 61850 tools and libraries.	Low	Medium	Provide vendor-neutral validation outputs and reproduce key behaviours using multivendor IEDs independent of proprietary tools.
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Note: Some replication risks are interlinked with the IPR/exploitation risks identified in D6.4 §5 (e.g., standardisation, partner commitment, market timing). Any major change in risk assessment (whether technical or IPR-related) will be reflected consistently in the updates of both D6.4 and D6.5.

5.2 Risks assessment and mitigation measures related to the TUD Digital Substation of the Future Laboratory

The TU Delft Digital Substation of the Future (DSoF) laboratory provides the real-time, cyber-physical environment required to validate virtualised protection and control functions, digital twins, and cyber-secure architectures under realistic conditions. While this VTL offers a comprehensive testing ecosystem based on RTDS real-time simulation, hardware-in-the-loop setups and advanced communication and cybersecurity infrastructures, several risks may affect the transferability of its results to external operators. The following table summarises the most relevant risks and the mitigation measures applied to ensure that the outcomes validated in the DSoF can be meaningfully interpreted and replicated in future deployments.

Table 3. Risk assessment and mitigation measures for the TUD Digital Substation of the Future Laboratory.

Risk ID	Risk description	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation strategy
R1	Limited replicability of RTDS real-time and hardware-in-the-loop capabilities.	Medium	High	Provide detailed documentation of real-time constraints and performance envelopes, allowing operators without RTDS to interpret results within realistic operational margins.

R2	Strict real-time performance requirements for vPAC may not be met by external infrastructures.	Medium	High	Report maximum allowable latencies, jitter sensitivity and response-time thresholds to guide operators in assessing whether their infrastructures can support validated functions.
R3	Dependence on advanced digital twins (power grid, IED, PAC) that are not available outside the DSoF.	Medium	Medium	Describe validated functionalities in a modular manner and indicate which validation steps require advanced models and which can be reproduced through simplified equivalents.
R4	Differences between the DSoF architecture and real-world substation architectures.	Medium	Medium	Provide functional and architectural abstractions showing minimum required components and equivalent configurations for operators with less advanced infrastructures.
R5	Limited transferability of cybersecurity and cyber-resilience test results.	Medium	Medium	Document attack scenarios, protection mechanisms and test conditions, enabling simplified or equivalent reproductions in environments with different cybersecurity capabilities.
R6	Variability in relay behaviour under complex fault and disturbance scenarios.	Low	Medium	Provide detailed descriptions of protection settings, fault conditions and operating zones to help extrapolate behaviour to systems with different configurations.

R7	Dependence on specific platforms (CRoF and Siemens Xcelerator).	Low	Medium	Highlight functions that are platform-independent and provide high-level alternatives or cloud-agnostic interpretations for operators without access to these platforms.
R8	Limited availability of specialised personnel to reproduce advanced DSoF validation activities.	Low	Medium	Specify required competence profiles and training needs, proposing equivalent skill sets for operators aiming to reproduce or interpret the validated functions.

6 Conclusions and Next Steps

This deliverable has defined the ESTELAR roadmap for technology advancement and maturity. The document clarifies the logical progression from architectural design and requirement consolidation to integrated laboratory validation in Virtual Test Laboratories, ensuring alignment with applicable standards, cybersecurity requirements, and interoperability principles.

The deliverable provides a coherent and realistic framework for tracking TRL progression throughout the project lifetime. In addition, it outlines a forward-looking post-project pathway, identifying steps for future replication, industrial adoption, and scale-up.

Overall, this roadmap supports a structured approach for technology development and validation in ESTELAR, establishing a solid guidance and foundation for laboratory-proven solutions at TRL 4, and enabling informed decision-making for potential follow-up initiatives beyond the project.

Future versions of D6.5 (and related deliverables D6.6, D6.7) will be kept consistent with updates to D6.4 (second and final versions).

Any changes in market sizing, KER list, or business models in updated D6.4 versions will automatically inform the replication roadmap and commercialisation pathways in subsequent D6.5 updates.